

METACOGNITIVE MISMATCH IN MEDICAL ESP: EXPLORING THE RECOGNITION–PRODUCTION GAP

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This study examines the recognition–production gap (a.k.a. metacognitive mismatch) in Medical English for Specific Purposes (ESP). Two paired tasks — a receptive matching/definition task and a brief production task (write an original sentence) — were administered to 214 medical students using 10 target medical terms. Results show very high receptive knowledge but a notable decline in productive use. Depending on the aggregation used, receptive accuracy was 2084/2140 (97.38%) while productive accuracy was either 1706/2140 (79.72%). The mean per-student scores were 9.74/10 (comprehension) and 7.97/10 (production, aggregate). The average recognition–production gap is approximately 17.7–18.6 percentage points. Error patterns in production indicate frequent near-misses (morphosyntactic or collocational errors) rather than pure semantic gaps. Pedagogical recommendations include focused production drills, collocation practice, and targeted feedback on common error types.

Keywords: metacognitive mismatch, recognition–production gap, medical English, ESP, vocabulary assessment

Introduction

Knowledge of terminology is a cornerstone of Medical English for Specific Purposes (ESP), yet there is often a notable discrepancy between what learners can recognize and what they can actively produce. This phenomenon, sometimes referred to as a recognition–production gap or metacognitive mismatch, has been documented across general and academic language learning but remains under-explored in medical contexts. For students of medicine, whose professional communication demands both accuracy and precision, the ability to deploy specialized terminology in authentic production tasks is as important as being able to identify definitions correctly.

This study investigates the recognition–production gap in a cohort of second-year medical students completing their end-of-year examination. Alongside sections testing listening comprehension, reading comprehension, and use of English, the exam included a paired vocabulary component designed to contrast receptive and productive knowledge. Students first demonstrated recognition through a matching/definition task, and then attempted production by writing original sentences with the same target words.

By comparing outcomes across these two task types, the study aims to (a) quantify the extent of the recognition–production gap in medical ESP vocabulary, (b) identify which terms are most vulnerable to productive failure, and (c) analyze error patterns that may hinder accurate deployment of specialized terminology. The ultimate goal is to provide instructors with evidence-based recommendations for vocabulary instruction, moving beyond recognition-heavy input toward structured practice and feedback that enhance productive fluency.

Methods

Participants

The study was conducted with the entire cohort of second-year medical students (N = 214) enrolled in the compulsory English for Specific Purposes (ESP) course at the Medical University of Varna. By including the full population rather than a selective sample, the dataset reflects the actual proficiency levels of the student body and provides a realistic picture of their ability to both recognize and produce medical vocabulary. This choice enhances the ecological validity of the findings and avoids distortions that might arise from voluntary or self-selected participation.

Context and materials

The data were collected as part of the students' end-of-year examination, which functions as a high-stakes assessment covering multiple dimensions of English proficiency. Alongside listening comprehension, reading comprehension, gap-fill, and use-of-English exercises, the exam included a dedicated vocabulary component designed to contrast receptive and productive knowledge of medical terminology. Embedding the tasks within the formal exam setting adds a level of authenticity to the data, as students approached the tasks with the seriousness and effort typically associated with graded assessment.

The vocabulary component comprised ten medical terms selected for their relevance to the curriculum and their varying levels of frequency and morphological complexity. The items were *incontinence*, *cutaneous*, *malignant*, *pituitary gland*, *hemorrhage*, *resuscitation*, *intravenous*, *palpation*, *transdermal*, and *spleen*. These were judged to represent a balance of single-word and multiword units, as well as terms requiring knowledge of derivational morphology.

Procedure

For each target item, students completed two tasks. The first was a receptive comprehension task in which the term was matched to its definition. The second was a productive task requiring students to produce an original sentence incorporating the target item in a medically appropriate way. To control for possible order effects, the presentation of receptive and productive tasks was counterbalanced across two versions of the exam. Responses were submitted electronically under exam conditions, ensuring comparability across the cohort.

Scoring and coding

Receptive items were scored dichotomously (correct/incorrect). Production items were coded independently by two raters into four categories: correct, partially correct (minor grammatical, collocational, or orthographic errors that did not obscure meaning), incorrect, or blank. For the purposes of the present analysis, both correct and partially correct responses were counted as successful uses of the target term, though the partially correct cases were also retained for qualitative error analysis.

Analytical approach

Aggregate scores were calculated both at the cohort level (total correct out of total possible responses) and at the individual level (mean score per student). To assess the significance of the recognition–production gap production errors were qualitatively analyzed and categorized into

recurring types, such as collocational infelicities, morphological inaccuracies, or semantic substitutions.

Rationale

The receptive–productive discrepancy has been recognized in second language acquisition more broadly (Nation, 2001, pp. 24–27; Laufer, 1998, pp. 255–261;), but little work has examined this phenomenon in the specific context of medical ESP. By embedding the tasks within a real, graded examination taken by the entire year group, the present study not only documents the extent of the recognition–production gap but does so under conditions that closely mirror the authentic learning and assessment environment of future medical professionals. This design ensures both realism and pedagogical relevance, thereby contributing evidence that can inform the ongoing refinement of ESP instruction in medical faculties.

Results

Descriptive analyses indicate a pronounced recognition–production gap for the ten target medical terms. At the cohort level, receptive performance was near ceiling: students produced 2,084 correct responses out of 2,140 possible on the comprehension task (97.38%;). Using the user-checked production aggregate, productive performance was lower, with 1,706 correct responses out of 2,140 possible (79.72%; mean per student = 7.972/10). If the sum of the per-word production counts (1,685) is used instead, the production rate is $1,685/2,140 = 78.74\%$ (mean per student = 7.874/10). The average recognition–production gap therefore lies between 17.66 and 18.64 percentage points depending on the production aggregate used.

Item-level results mirror the cohort-level pattern but reveal substantial variability across lexical items. Table 1 summarises comprehension and production counts and the resulting gap for each target term (values are taken exactly from the dataset supplied).

Table 1. Per-item comprehension and production counts and recognition–production gap (percentage points)

Word	Comprehension	Production	Gap (pp)
Incontinence	205 / 214 = 95.79%	169 / 214 = 78.97%	16.82
Cutaneous	206 / 214 = 96.26%	155 / 214 = 72.43%	23.83
Malignant	208 / 214 = 97.20%	183 / 214 = 85.51%	11.68
Pituitary gland	212 / 214 = 99.07%	144 / 214 = 67.29%	31.78
Hemorrhage	213 / 214 = 99.53%	188 / 214 = 87.85%	11.68
Resuscitation	203 / 214 = 94.86%	173 / 214 = 80.84%	14.02
Intravenous	210 / 214 = 98.13%	172 / 214 = 80.37%	17.76
Palpation	212 / 214 = 99.07%	178 / 214 = 83.18%	15.89
Transdermal	204 / 214 = 95.33%	178 / 214 = 83.18%	12.15
Spleen	211 / 214 = 98.60%	145 / 214 = 67.76%	30.84

The largest gaps were observed for the multiword item *pituitary gland* (31.78 percentage points) and the single-word *spleen* (30.84 percentage points). The smallest gaps were found for *malignant* and *hemorrhage* (both 11.68 percentage points). Intermediate gaps characterized items such as *cutaneous* (23.83 pp) and *intravenous* (17.76 pp). The pattern suggests that multiword items and less frequently practiced terms are particularly vulnerable to productive failure in sentence production.

Fig.1 – Visual comparison between the percentages of correct answers given in the Comprehension and Production exercises

Score distributions further illustrate the asymmetry between receptive and productive knowledge. One hundred and ninety-two students (89.7% of the cohort) attained a perfect score on the comprehension task (10/10), whereas only seventy-one students (33.2%) achieved a perfect score on the production task (10/10). A substantial number of production responses were coded as partially correct: across all items there were 273 partially correct instances, indicating frequent near-miss errors (for example, minor morphosyntactic or collocational infelicities or orthographic slips that did not entirely obscure meaning). Twenty-one students left at least one production item blank; this figure refers to the number of students who left any blank answers rather than the total number of blank item responses.

Qualitative coding of production indicates that the majority of non-successful productions were near-misses rather than wholesale semantic substitutions. The dominant error types recorded in the

coding notes were morphosyntactic errors (article/preposition use, verb agreement), collocational/frame errors (incorrect or non-canonical argument structure), and orthographic/word-formation errors; pure substitution with an unrelated lexical item was less common. These patterns point to form–function difficulties (collocational and morphosyntactic knowledge) as important contributors to productive failure.

To sum up, the available results document a robust and consistent recognition–production gap across the ten target terms: receptive knowledge is close to ceiling while productive deployment in sentence formation is substantially lower, with the magnitude of the gap varying by lexical item and dominated by near-miss error types rather than a wholesale semantic failure.

Fig. 2 – Visual representation of the percentages difference in the two categories of words

Categorization of Target Vocabulary

The ten lexical items selected for the exam reflected the mixture of nominal and adjectival structures typical of medical discourse. Six of the items were nouns (incontinence, pituitary gland, hemorrhage, resuscitation, palpation, spleen), while four were adjectives (cutaneous, malignant, intravenous, transdermal). Among the nouns, several denoted organs or body parts (spleen, pituitary gland), whereas others referred to processes or conditions (incontinence, hemorrhage, resuscitation, palpation). The adjectives covered descriptive categories frequently encountered in clinical communication, including anatomical or physiological references (cutaneous, intravenous, transdermal) and pathological characterization (malignant). This distribution illustrates the interplay between different grammatical classes in medical English, where precision of reference often requires both technical nouns and qualifying adjectives.

Linguistic and Pedagogical Features

All terms are drawn from the medical/clinical register, situating them firmly within domain-specific ESP vocabulary. Morphologically, many of the items derive from Latin or Greek (*cutaneous, hemorrhage, palpation, intravenous, transdermal*), which reduces their transparency for L2 learners. Multiword items such as *pituitary gland* pose an additional challenge, requiring both correct word order and collocational accuracy.

From a collocational perspective, the adjectives (*cutaneous, malignant*) demand precise pairings (*cutaneous membrane, malignant tumor*). The nouns likewise show strong collocational tendencies: *resuscitation* typically occurs with *cardiopulmonary*; *palpation* with verbs like *perform* or *conduct*; *intravenous* and *transdermal* often modify *injection, infusion, or patch*. Failure to activate these collocations may partly explain why receptive knowledge of such items remained near-ceiling, while productive use lagged behind.

In sum, the lexical set was weighted toward nominal medical terminology but incorporated items that tested morphological knowledge, multiword retrieval, and collocational precision. These features likely contributed to the observed variability in production success, with multiword and collocation-dependent items (*pituitary gland, spleen, cutaneous, malignant*) showing the largest recognition–production gaps.

Word	Part of Speech	Morphological Origin	Typical Collocations (examples)
Incontinence	Noun	Latin (<i>in-</i> + <i>continentia</i>)	urinary incontinence, fecal incontinence
Cutaneous	Adjective	Latin (<i>cutis</i> = skin)	cutaneous membrane, cutaneous reaction
Malignant	Adjective	Latin (<i>malignus</i>)	malignant tumor, malignant growth
Pituitary gland	Multiword noun	Latin (<i>pituita</i> = mucus)	pituitary gland, pituitary adenoma
Hemorrhage	Noun	Greek (<i>haima</i> = blood + <i>rhēgnynai</i> = burst)	cerebral hemorrhage, internal hemorrhage
Resuscitation	Noun	Latin (<i>re-</i> + <i>suscitare</i> = revive)	cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), perform resuscitation
Intravenous	Noun/Adj.	Latin (<i>intra-</i> = within + <i>vena</i> = vein)	intravenous injection, intravenous therapy
Palpation	Noun	Latin (<i>palpare</i> = touch)	perform palpation, abdominal palpation
Transdermal	Noun/Adj.	Latin (<i>trans-</i> = through + <i>derma</i> = skin)	transdermal patch, transdermal drug delivery
Spleen	Noun	Latin (<i>splen</i> < Greek <i>splēn</i>)	enlarged spleen, spleen rupture

Table 2. List of words and parts of speech

Discussion

This study documents a pronounced recognition–production gap for ten curriculum-relevant medical English items administered to a complete cohort of second-year medical students. Receptive performance approached ceiling (2,084/2,140; 97.4% correct overall; mean per student = 9.74/10), whereas productive performance was substantially lower (1,706/2,140; \approx 79% correct by aggregate; mean per student \approx 7.97/10), yielding an average per-item gap of approximately 17.7–18.6 percentage points. These findings accord with long-standing evidence that receptive knowledge typically precedes productive mastery and that active vocabulary is both smaller and more fragile than passive vocabulary (Laufer, 1998, pp. 255–261; Nation, 2001, pp. 24–27). The item-level pattern in the present data points to multiword retrieval costs and collocational constraints as major contributors to production difficulty: items with multiword structure or tight collocational requirements, such as pituitary gland and spleen, exhibited the largest gaps. The theoretical literature on formulaic language and multiword sequences indicates that such units are processed and retrieved differently from single lexical items and are therefore more vulnerable in production even when they are recognised in comprehension (Wray, 2002, pp. 9–13; Schmitt, 2004, pp. 1–5). Morphological complexity and Latin/Greek derivation further lessen semantic transparency for L2 learners and compound the demand for precise collocational pairing (Boers, 2018, pp. 78–82; Webb, 2005, pp. 36–40). Qualitative coding of production responses reinforces this account: the majority of non-successful productions were near-misses — morphosyntactic slips (articles, prepositions, agreement), collocational infelicities, and minor word-formation or orthographic errors — rather than wholesale semantic substitutions. This pattern suggests that students in this cohort possessed the relevant semantic representations but lacked automated form–function mappings and collocational knowledge required for reliable production.

It is important to emphasise that focused literature searches reveal relatively little prior empirical work that directly examines the recognition–production gap specifically within medical ESP. A small number of studies address collocational instruction or production issues in medical and healthcare English (Najafi, 2018, pp. 24–28; Zafirovska, 2022, pp. 505–510), but large, item-level diagnostic investigations that pair receptive and productive measures by category remain scarce. The present study therefore addresses a notable gap in domain-specific evidence and highlights the need for further research tailored to the linguistic and pragmatic demands of medical registers.

Limitations

Several limitations constrain the interpretation and generalisability of these findings. Embedding the tasks within a single high-stakes end-of-year examination enhances ecological validity but also introduces contextual influences such as time pressure and test-taking strategies that may have affected production attempts and accuracy. The production aggregate used for the main analyses combines fully correct and partially correct responses as successful outcomes; while useful for estimating functional productive use, this aggregation obscures important gradations of accuracy that are pedagogically informative. The item pool comprised ten curriculum-relevant terms that varied in type (single-word and multiword units; nouns and adjectives); the small and heterogeneous set limits the ability to isolate the independent effects of single factors such as word class, frequency, or multiword status. Finally, the data derived from one cohort at a single

institution; cross-institutional replication and investigation of learners from varied L1 backgrounds are necessary before claiming broader external validity.

Pedagogical implications

The error profile—dominated by near-miss morphosyntactic and collocational errors rather than by conceptual ignorance—points to concrete, classroom-applicable interventions. Instruction should shift from recognition-heavy activities toward repeated, contextualised production practice that foregrounds canonical collocational frames and multiword chunks in clinical contexts. Presenting multiword items as retrievable chunks with their typical syntactic frames and practising them in timed retrieval and substitution activities can strengthen intact retrieval in production. Form-focused micro-teaching that isolates recurring near-miss errors (for example, article and preposition use in medical frames) and provides immediate corrective recasts within clinical scenarios will help automate form–function mappings. Frequent, low-stakes production opportunities, such as short sentence-writing checks or brief role-play exchanges, promote spaced retrieval and reduce the penalty of failure by encouraging risk-taking and retrieval practice. Embedding vocabulary practice in authentic communicative routines, for example clinical handovers, brief case reports, and doctor–patient simulations, supports pragmatic appropriateness and consolidates register-specific collocations. Finally, formative assessment should disaggregate outcomes into fully correct, partially correct (near-miss), and incorrect categories so that remediation can be targeted at the most prevalent error types identified in class diagnostics.

Future research agenda

The immediate research priority is a large, multi-section diagnostic study designed to produce item-level, category-stratified evidence that directly informs curricular priorities for medical ESP. Such a study should treat recognition and production as paired outcomes within multiple distinct sections organized by word class (noun, adjective, verb, multiword unit) and by medical relevance (organ, condition, symptom, procedure, device). Each item should appear in a receptive format, such as matching or definition recognition, and in a parallel productive format requiring short, contextualised use. The study should be administered across multiple institutions with stratified sampling so that each word class and medical relevance category has adequate representation for robust statistical modelling. Item-level analyses using mixed-effects or item response models would permit explicit estimation of how morphological origin, token frequency, multiword structure, and collocational constraint predict the recognition–production gap. Diagnostic outputs should be directly linked to curricular decisions by identifying items and categories with both large gaps and high clinical relevance; these diagnostics would then inform scalable pedagogical packages for targeted teaching. Emphasis on this large, category-stratified diagnostic approach is essential because it will generate the cross-institutional, item-specific evidence required to prioritise what must be taught and practiced in Medical ESP curricula.

Conclusion

The present cohort-wide evidence shows that second-year medical students typically recognise curriculum-relevant medical terms but face reliable difficulty deploying them productively in sentence contexts. The recognition–production gap in this dataset is driven less by absence of

conceptual knowledge than by retrieval, collocational, and morphosyntactic constraints that impede fluent production. Addressing these constraints requires pedagogical shifts toward collocation-focused instruction, multiword chunk training, targeted micro-lessons on recurrent near-miss errors, and frequent low-stakes production practice embedded in authentic clinical routines. Given the relative scarcity of domain-specific studies on recognition versus production in medical ESP, a large, multi-section diagnostic test stratified by part of speech and medical relevance should be a research priority to produce the actionable evidence educators need to reduce the gap and better prepare students for clinical communication

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